

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Mom, C., van den Besselaar, P., & Möller, T. (2022). Factors influencing the academic career – an event history analysis. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22138). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6975566>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Factors influencing the academic career – an event history analysis¹

Charlie Mom^{*}, Peter van den Besselaar^{**} and Torger Möller^{***}

^{*} charlie@teresamom.com

TMC Research, Middenweg 203, Amsterdam, 1098 AN (Amsterdam)

^{**} p.a.a.vanden.besselaar@vu.nl; peter@teresamom.com

Faculty of Social Sciences, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, (Netherlands).

^{***} moeller@dzhw.eu

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW), Schützenstrasse 6a, Berlin, 10117 (Germany)

Introduction

The question whether women suffer from gender bias in academic careers remains on both the political agenda and the scientific agenda. Three observations on studies into who attains full professorship are worth mentioning: (i) Several studies do not take performance into account (e.g. Box-Steffensmeier et al. 2015), which makes it impossible to distinguish gender *disparities* from gender bias (Cruz Castro, Sanz-Menéndez 2019). However, recent studies tend to include performance variables (Jonkers 2011; Sanz-Menéndez et al. 2013; Schröder et al. 2019; Lutter et al. 2022). (ii) Most of these studies use an event history analysis (Allison 2014; McGinnes et al. 1982), which has become a standard approach for academic career studies. In this way, careers are studied as processes over time, which goes beyond traditional correlational approaches. Some of these studies found that women have a slower career (Jonkers 2011, Sanz-Menendez et al 2013), although in the latter study the effect was non-significant. In contrast, Schröder et al. (2021) and Lutter et al. (2022) found that women have a non-significant higher probability to get a tenured professorship than men, when controlling for publication performance (although the way of measuring output seems problematic in those studies). (iii) Experimental approaches have been developed in order to identify causal effects (Williams & Ceci 2015; Ceci & Williams 2015). These authors did two survey-experiments where faculty had to rank hypothetical applicants for tenure-track positions, and they concluded that there is a 2-1 preference for female candidates when men and women are equally qualified. At the same time, when men were rated higher, the preference for women disappeared. However, the external validity of these studies may be low, as other research shows that women are generally seen as less qualified than men, also when performance is controlled for (Van den Besselaar & Mom 2021; Bol et al 2022). Furthermore, the two experiments do not take the effects of group decision-making into consideration.

In our study, we use real data to maximize external validity. In order to come as close to causal analysis, we use an event history analysis which is based on developments over time.

¹ The work was supported by grant nr. 824574 of the EC: The GRANted project (2019-2023).

The case

The case consists of researchers who received their PhD between 2000 and 2005 from the same Dutch university, in a variety of fields: natural sciences, mathematics, computer science, earth and life sciences, medical sciences, economics and psychology. For this sample, we can analyze their careers over a 16-years period. In the Netherlands, the period between the PhD and being appointed as full professor takes on average 17 to 19 years (Rathenau Institute 2018, 2019), which implies that our study covers early professor appointments only: the average duration in our sample is 12.75 years, counting the year of receiving the PhD as year 1. From our knowledge of the Dutch system, we assume indeed two groups of professor appointments could be distinguished, the early professor appointments based on excellent research performance, and the later appointments based on a larger set of achievements, including teaching and managerial roles. If that is correct, the explanation of those two types of careers may need two different models.

Early(-ier) professor appointments are based on research achievements, and relevant factors would be the number of publications and their impact, and the successful application for prestigious grants, which do have a positive effect on the academic career (Van den Besselaar & Sandstrom 2016). In the Dutch context, this are the VENI and VIDI grants, as well as the ERC Starting Grant. The grants are only counted if they were obtained before the appointment as full professor.

Data

The dataset consists of 971 researchers that obtained the PhD degree in period 2000-2005.² Data about PhD holders are available from open sources, among others from the published PhD-theses. The sample covers all PhD graduates of one of the Dutch universities, which has the advantage that we do not suffer from self-selection. We only include the fields mentioned above, where journal article based bibliometric performance indicators can be considered meaningful.

We collected information about gender, age, year of PhD (= academic age), mobility, and the years when a national or international career grant was obtained.

- Data about academic age, age, and research field can be retrieved from the electronic or printed versions of the PhD theses.
- Mobility data can be derived from the bibliometric dataset (identifying changes in institutional affiliations). This also holds for data about ending an academic career (no publications anymore after a certain year)
- The Narcis database provides data on the Dutch career grants, and ERC career grant winners come from the ERC website.
- Data about gender were derived using the first name of the participants, and where these were unknown, we used the web to find this.
- The data for careers (appointment to full or associate professor) cover the period until 2021 and were also retrieved from the Narcis database.
- Online searches for LinkedIn, ResearchGate, and homepages were done to identify international careers leading to full professorships outside of the Netherlands.
- We searched for all researchers their Scopus ID, which was used to identify all publications.

² One case was excluded since that person received professorship prior to receiving the PhD. 6

- Three bibliometric performance indicators were calculated year by year for the period 1996-2020 using Scopus via the *Competence Network for Bibliometrics* at the DZHW (Berlin). The three bibliometric performance indicators are:
 - o The fractionalized number of publications
 - o The fractional number of top 10% highly cited publications.
 - o A journal impact indicator.

In this paper we use three performance indicators, namely whether the PhD thesis was awarded cum laude (best grade), the fractionalized number published papers, and the number of prestigious grants. For the last two indicators, the score in year N equals the sum of the scores over the years 1 to N. We calculated the indicators at annual basis, in order to use those as independent time-varying variables in an *Event History Analysis*.

Given the sample, we can observe the career over a period between 16 years (for those graduating in 2005: 2005-2020) and 21 years (for those graduating in 2000: 2000-2020). In our analysis – as explained below - we only use the first 16 years of the career.

Method

We deploy *event history analysis* (Allison 2014; Sanz-Menéndez, et al. 2013), which is suited for predicting the occurrence of an event (appointment as full professor at a certain moment), using independent variables that change on a year by year basis such as the number of scholarly publications and grants, or that are constant such as cum laude for the PhD thesis, the research field (faculty) and gender.

As our data are available at a yearly basis, we use a discrete (versus a continuous) time analysis, which is a logistic regression with all person/year combinations as cases. This type of event history analysis requires that the career lengths of the participants are equal (here 16 years), and three groups of participants can be distinguished: those promoted to full professor within this 16-years period; those leaving academia within the period (operationalized as stop publishing); and those remaining in the system, but not promoted to full professor within the period under consideration (but may become professor later in the career). The last two groups are ‘censored’ in the study. Below we analyze whether the outcomes are sensitive for censoring the leavers (Allison 2014). The analysis is done using a logistic regression (STATA/BE 17.0), with every person/year combination as a case.

The model

Our model³ explains becoming a full professor in terms of academic performance (number of fractional counted papers, prestigious grants, cum laude for the PhD thesis⁴), whereas controlling for gender, academic age, year of the PhD, and research field.

Academic age may have a more complex impact: One would assume that there is a hesitation to appoint very young researchers as full professor, as those may not have had time to develop other skills needed for that position, such as being able to manage a research team. As a consequence, one would expect that the variable *academic age* has a positive impact on the probability to be appointed as a full professor. At the same time, getting academically older may after some moment also have a negative impact on the probability to be promoted to full professor, as then the competition by the next upcoming generation may get an impact. Therefore, we expect that the variable *academic age squared* will have a negative effect. The

³ Based on Allison 2014

⁴ In the Dutch context, cum laude for the PhD thesis is an important distinction: only about 5% of the PhD theses are awarded cum laude (Van den Besselaar, Mom, Van de Broek, forthcoming).

duration until a full professor appointment may be different between faculties, but testing this with an interaction variable *faculty*academic age* showed that this is not the case. Therefore, we exclude this interaction variable from the analysis. Finally, the effect of performance may differ between men and women, and therefore we also include two interaction terms: *gender*grants* and *gender*papers*.

Are the selected indicators for academic merit valid? An appointment to full professor requires more qualities than only publications with impact and prestigious grants, but also teaching qualities and social and managerial skills (Van Arensbergen et al. 2014). However, it is a reasonable assumption that appointments as a full professor at a relatively young academic age are mainly based on research performance, whereas a wider set of qualifications and becomes important for professor appointments at a later age.

Table 1. Variables in the model

Variable	Description
Faculty	Dummy variable for each of the faculties included
Gender	Male (1) versus female (0)
PhD year	Year in which the PhD was awarded
Cum laude	Cum laude = 1, else = 0
Fractional papers	Cumulative over years, centered
Number of grants	Cumulative
Academic age	Years since PhD
Academic age squared	Years since PhD squared
Academic age * faculty	Interaction term
Gender*number of grants	Interaction term
Gender*frac papers	Interaction term

Findings

Table 2 presents the findings of the analysis. First of all, the control variables *faculty* were included to control for faculty differences in the career patterns in the various faculties of the university.

The effect of the *academic age* and *academic age-squared* are as expected, and the *PhD year* is not significant, nor is the *PhD year*.

The academic output (in terms of *fractionalized publications*) has a significant positive effect on getting appointed as a full professorship, as has the number of *prestigious grants*. Those that got a *cum laude* for the PhD thesis have a (non-significant) higher probability to become full professor.

Finally, it is also clear that – after controlling for the academic performance variables, and the year of the appointment, also the variable *gender* has an effect on the probability of becoming full professor, with an odds ratio of 2.71 which is fairly high.

Table 2. Predicting the probability of becoming full professor

Logistic regression	Number observations	=	11114		
	LR chi2(10)	=	124.33		
	Prob > chi2	=	0		
Log likelihood = -441.60196	Pseudo R2	=	0.1234		
	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P>z	95% Conf. Interval
faculty 6	0.835	0.371	-0.41	0.684	0.349 1.993
faculty 7	1.626	0.761	1.04	0.299	0.649 4.071
faculty 8	2.183	0.938	1.82	0.069	0.941 5.065
faculty 9	1	(empty)			
faculty 10	1.083	0.396	0.22	0.828	0.528 2.219
Gender (male=1)	2.708	0.897	3.01	0.003	1.415 5.183
Cum laude (CL=1)	1.480	0.628	0.92	0.356	0.644 3.399
PhD year	1.033	0.072	0.46	0.647	0.900 1.184
Fractional papers	2.642	0.440	5.84	0	1.907 3.661
Grants	1.255	0.104	2.74	0.006	1.067 1.476
Academic age	1.348	0.173	2.34	0.019	1.049 1.733
Academic age^2	0.986	0.007	-2.05	0.04	0.973 0.999
Gender *public.	0.523	0.089	-3.81	0	0.374 0.730
Gender * grants	0.903	0.107	-0.87	0.386	0.716 1.138

Robustness check

The outcomes are influenced by the participants that leave for some reason the sample, in this case by moving out of academia, and these are the ‘randomly censored’ cases (Allison 2014). To control whether this has influence on the findings, we implemented the following check: All participants remain in the analysis over the whole period, also those that left academia. The latter group gets for the years they were not in academia anymore for all variables the same values as in the last year they were still in. Table 3 shows the results of this analysis.

Most of the estimated odds ratios in Table 3 remain similar to the findings presented in Table 2, apart from one substantial difference. The effect of gender becomes much stronger, which suggests an even larger bias in favor of men. This difference can be explained as the leaky pipeline effect: All men and women that left academia are included in the analysis of Table 3, and this group consists of considerably more women than men – much more women than men left the system. Overall, one would conclude that the presented analysis in Table 2 is robust but includes only one aspect of gender bias, the glass ceiling, and not the leaky pipeline.

Table 3. Predicting the probability of becoming full professor (all remain in the analysis)

Logistic regression	Number observations	=	22027			
	LR chi2(10)	=	213.3			
	Prob > chi2	=	0			
Log likelihood = -456.10944	Pseudo R2	=	0.1895			
	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	z	P>z	95% Conf. Interval	
faculty 6	0.715	0.318	-0.76	0.45	0.299	1.709
faculty 7	1.744	0.825	1.18	0.24	0.690	4.409
faculty 8	2.608	1.123	2.23	0.026	1.122	6.064
faculty 9	1	(empty)				
faculty 10	1.191	0.438	0.48	0.634	0.580	2.448
Gender (male=1)	3.730	1.330	3.69	0	1.855	7.501
Cum laude (CL=1)	1.435	0.623	0.83	0.405	0.613	3.359
PhD year	1.025	0.071	0.35	0.73	0.893	1.176
Fractional papers	2.441	0.316	6.88	0	1.893	3.147
Grants	1.180	0.072	2.72	0.007	1.047	1.329
Academic age	1.511	0.153	4.07	0	1.239	1.843
Academic age^2	0.980	0.005	-3.72	0	0.969	0.990
Gender *public.	0.549	0.073	-4.51	0	0.423	0.713
Gender * grants	0.958	0.083	-0.49	0.623	0.809	1.135

Conclusions and discussion

In this paper we used an event history analysis to investigate whether grants do have an effect on appointments as full professor, and whether there are gender differences in career success. After controlling for several variables (academic performance, faculty, academic age, cum laude), we found that grants and gender do have an effect, and the odds ratios suggest a considerable effect of gender. The Pseudo-R2 of the analysis is 0.1234.

The robustness check suggests that most of the findings are not much influenced by the random censoring (the participants leaving the system), but this does not apply to the gender variable: much more women leave the system than men, and therefore the level of gender bias is most likely underestimated. The Pseudo-R2 of the analysis of the robustness check is 0.1895.

The findings do suggest that grants are rather influential for academic careers in the Dutch context – even more for women than for men, which means that grant selection should be very valid in order to have fair career chances. Above that, and after controlling for grants and for other performance dimensions, appointments to full professor still show considerable gender bias, at least for the cohorts between 2000 and 2005 – the younger generations of today's professors.

In a next version we will add a few other explanatory variables, like the ERC grants and add the *predictive margins* for the logistic regression, in order to analyze the effects of gender on the outcomes more in detail.

Acknowledgements

The work for this paper was supported by grant nr. 824574 of the EC: The GRANted project (2019-2023).

References

Allison, P. D. (2014). *Event history analysis and survival analysis*. Sage Research Methods. London, Sage.

Bol, T, de Vaan, M., & Van de Rijdt, A. (2022). Gender-equal funding rates conceal unequal evaluations. *Research Policy*, *51*(1), 104399.

Box-Steffensmeier, J. M., Cunha, R. C., Varbanov, R. A., Hoh, Y. S., Knisley, M. L., & Holmes, M. A. (2015). Survival Analysis of Faculty Retention and Promotion in the Social Sciences by Gender. *PLoS ONE*, *10*(11), e0143093.

Ceci, S. J, & Williams, W. M. (2015). Women have substantial advantage in STEM faculty hiring, except when competing against more-accomplished men. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *6*,1532.

Cruz-Castro, L., & Sanz-Menéndez, L. (2019). *Grant allocation disparities from a gender perspective: Literature review*. GRANteD project D1.1.

Jonkers, K. (2011). Mobility, productivity, gender and career development of Argentinean life scientists. *Research Evaluation*, *20*(5), 411–421

Lutter, M., Habicht, I. M., & Schröder, M. (2022). Gender differences in the determinants of becoming a professor in Germany. An event history analysis of academic psychologists from 1980 to 2019. *Research Policy*, *51*, 104506

McGinnis, R., Allison, P. D., & Long, J. S. (1982). Postdoctoral training in bioscience: Allocation and outcomes. *Social Forces*, *60*(3), 701-722

Möller, T., Van den Besselaar, P., & Mom, C. (2022). What is researcher independence and how can it be measured?. In *Proceedings STI 2022*.

Rathenau Institute. (2018). *Fact sheet: Women in science*. January 19, 2018.

Rathenau Institute. (2019). *The share of new female professors rising faster than expected*. March 8, 2019.

Sanz-Menéndez, L., Cruz-Castro, L., & Alva, K. (2013). Time to tenure in Spanish Universities: an event history analysis. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(10), e77028.

Schroder, M., Lutter, M., & Habicht, I. M. (2021). Publishing, signaling, social capital, and gender: Determinants of becoming a tenured professor in German political science. *PLoS ONE*, *16*(1), e0243514.

Van Arensbergen, P., van der Weijden, I., & van den Besselaar, P. (2014). Different views on scholarly talent: What are the talents we are looking for in science?. *Research Evaluation*, *23*(4), 273-284.

Van den Besselaar, P., & Mom, C. (2021). Gender differences in research grant allocation - a mixed picture. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.13641*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.13641>

Van den Besselaar, P., Mom, T., & Van de Broek, T. (forthcoming). *Gender bias in awards: the case of cum laude for the PhD thesis*.

Van den Besselaar, P. & Sandström, U. (2016). Gender differences in research performance and in academic careers. *Scientometrics*, *106*, 143–162

Van den Besselaar, P., & Sandström, U. (2019). Measuring Researcher Independence Using Bibliometric Data: A Proposal for a New Performance Indicator. *PLoS ONE*, *14*(3), e0202712.

Williams, W. M., & Ceci, S. J. (2015). National hiring experiments reveal 2:1 faculty preference for women on STEM tenure track. *PNAS*, *112*(17), 5360–5365.